

Examination of the Oil of *Clupea Ilisha*.

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Clupea Ilisha is found abundantly in the rivers of Bengal and Burma. The output is so large that after supplying the entire rainy season, fishermen saltup the surplus to sell in winter when this variety of fish is scarce. In this salting process much of the oil comes out and as such is practically lost. With a view to finding out some technical utilisation of this oil the present work was undertaken.

The fish is very cheap in proper season. It yields about 20 per cent. oil on being simply boiled with saline water, retaining its shape if carefully handled.

The oil is characterised by its pale yellow colour, fat like consistency, slight fishy odour and low iodine value. In all these properties the oil can be differentiated from marine fish oils,

An examination of the oil gave the following values.

Consistency and colour	Like butter fat.
Specific gravity at 23°	0.9194
Refractive index at 40°	1.4606
Saponification value	200.0
Iodine value	88.0
R. W. value	1.7
Poianeske value	0.77
Acid value	2.19
Unsaponifiable matter	0.85 p.c.

Though the oil contains a large proportion of linoleic acid together with clupanodonic acid (8 p.c.), the oil film when exposed to atmosphere for about a month, did not show any appreciable sign of drying, indicating thereby the non-drying character of the oil. The oil separates into its solid and liquid fractions on standing at a temperature of 30°. The solid fraction has a melting point of 46° and a setpoint of 36°, whereas the same for the liquid fraction are

21° and 10° respectively. The mixed fatty acids were examined and found to contain 37·4 per cent. solid acid and 56·3 per cent. liquid acids. The liquid acids were further separated by Bromide method and gave oleic acid, 57 p.c., linoleic acid, 35 p. c. and clupanodonic acid, 8 p.c., whereas the solid acid was almost entirely constituted of palmitic acid. The unsaponifiable matter was examined and was found to contain cholesterol. During the examination of fatty acids, a dirty mass having strong fishy odour was liberated when the dry soap obtained by saponifying the oil, was acidified with hydrochloric acid. It was practically insoluble in ether but dissolved easily in alkalis. As the quantity was very small it could not be examined further. The oil responded to the test for vitamin D and gave soft soap on saponification with caustic soda, both the properties are technically utilisable.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Examination of the Mixed Fatty Acids.

The oil was saponified with alcoholic potash and alcohol driven off. The dried soap obtained was first extracted with petroleum ether to remove unsaponifiable matter, then decomposed by dilute hydrochloric acid and the liberated fatty acid layer was washed free from mineral acids. It was examined and the following values were obtained.

Iodine value	90·5
Mean mol. wt.	268·5
Melting point	42°

The mixed fatty acids were separated into liquid and solid fractions by the method of Twitchell (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806), and the following results were obtained.

	p.c.	Iodine value.	M.p.
Solid acids	37·4	1·75	57°
Liquid acids	56·3	144·5	...

Examination of the Oil by Alcoholysis.

50 C.c. of the oil were submitted to alcoholysis using POCl_3 (Goswami and Ramanujam, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 413).

The resulting ester freed from acids, glycerine and moisture was distilled under 5 mm. pressure with the result given below.

Temperature.		Fractions.
Upto 170°	...	Traces
170°—190°	...	17 c.c.
190°—212°	...	24 c.c.

A black residue having strong fishy odour remained undistilled even above 230°. Results of the distillation point out the following:

(a) Practical absence of lower acids. This is corroborated by low Reichert value.

(b) Presence of palmitic acid to the extent of 40 p. c. of the total acid. This has been supported by the separation of acid as given above and by the study of solid acid as is given hereafter.

Examination of the Solid Fatty Acid.

The solid fatty acid as obtained by separating the mixed fatty acid was esterified in methyl alcohol by passing a current of dry HCl gas. Ester obtained was a white liquid at ordinary temperature but solidified when cooled into plates, m. p. 26°. This was distilled under vacuum with the result given below.

Temperature.	Pressure.	Fractions.
Up to 170°	... 5 mm.	Traces
170°—190°	... „	Entire content

From the result of the distillation it seems probable that the distillate is constituted of methyl palmitate.

The distilled ester was saponified by alcoholic potash and fatty acids liberated by hydrochloric acid. This was crystallised 5 times from absolute alcohol and the crystals gave m. p. 59° and molecular weight 263 corresponding figures for palmitic acid being 61° and 256. The lead salt was prepared and crystallised from alcohol melting at 109°; lead palmitate melts at 112°. It therefore seems probable that the solid acid is mostly constituted of palmitic acid.

Examination of Liquid Fatty Acid.

The liquid fatty acid as separated by Twitchells method was brominated in dry ethereal solution by bromine in presence of glacial acetic acid. Ether insoluble bromides being filtered off, the solution was washed with thiosulphate solution to remove excess of bromine. The residue obtained after distilling off the ether, was boiled with petroleum ether and cooled over night in an ice chest. The separated crystals were filtered and the mother liquor was little concentrated, then again cooled, when a second crop of crystals was obtained. The process was repeated thrice when no further crystals appeared. Results obtained are given below.

Bromide.	M. p.	Inference.
Insoluble in ether	Decomposes at 200°	Octabromide
Insoluble in ether but soluble in benzene		Hexabromide absent
Insoluble in petroleum ether	113°	Tetrabromide
Soluble in petroleum ether	Oil	Dibromide

From the above result it is evident that clupanodonic acid, linoleic acid and oleic acid are present in the oil. The percentages of the acids as given before were calculated from the amount of bromides.

Unsaponifiable matter.—The oil after saponification with caustic potash was extracted with petroleum ether from which its percentage was determined after evaporating off the solvent. The residue was crystallised from alcohol and crystals obtained were found to be those of cholesterol.

Vitamins.—Vitamin A was tested for by antimony trichloride (*Analyst*, 1928, 53, 156). There was no coloration at first but after a few minutes a violet colour developed which gradually turned into deep red. This is considered to be good colour reaction for vitamin D. But the absence of blue coloration at the beginning shows the absence of vitamin A. Vitamin D was further examined by Shears test (*Proc. Soc. Expt. and Biol. Medicine*, 1928, 23, 546.)